

Social Skills, Self-Awareness of Social Studies Teachers and Social Adjustment of Upper Basic Social Studies Students in Delta State, Nigeria

Nancy Isioma **Abogoh** & Peter Ogbianigene **Dania**

Department of Social Science Education, Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria.

Abstract

The research was designed to investigate social skills, self-awareness of Social Studies teachers and social adjustment of upper basic Social Studies students in Delta State, Nigeria. To direct the study, two hypotheses were formulated. The study was hinged on behaviourist theory. This study adopted correlation research design. The population of the study consists of 385 teachers and 6,696 Students with a sample of 40 Teachers and 200 Students in upper basic schools in Delta State. The techniques adapted for sampling of sample in the study were the stratified random sampling techniques which involves the use of tailoring procedure for the study. The instrument for data collection were questionnaire and Social Studies Students examination score and grade for basic eight, 2022/2023 academic session. The instruments for data collection were face and content validated by experts in guidance and counseling, and measurement and evaluation. The study employed correlation coefficient of determination, regression analysis and F-test were used to test the stated hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Findings showed that Social Skills and self – awareness affect the social adjustment of Social Studies Students Based on the findings, it was suggested that teachers should enhance the promotion of social skills and self – awareness of students.

Keywords: Social skills, Self - awareness, Social Studies teachers, Social adjustment, Nigeria

Introduction

The future of any nation to a very large extent is contingent upon the quality of teachers. Those to be recruited as teachers should be people who have demonstrated some measure of competence in knowledge and skills as well as possess a healthy attitude for the achievement of the educational objectives. As the population of the school age children grows, the problem of increased demand for qualified teachers also persists. Thus, making the teaching profession the largest employment career in the world (Babalola, 2017). Nevertheless, in spite of the growing number of teachers on government payroll, the social adjustment of secondary school students seems not to have satisfactorily improved as expected.

Social skills according to Goleman (2019) refers to abilities of communication, cooperation and team working, handling disputes and effective negotiations, organizing and effectively implementing actions, the ability to learn how to learn. It is the effective communication, teamwork, dispute management, acceptance of constant changes and developments, flexibility and adaptability, taking initiatives and risks (Wahlster, 2011; Kully-Martenset. al. 2012). The term 'skills' determines the way an individual performs a series of actions, in terms of speed, accuracy and efficiency. Skills refer to the dynamic implementation of an activity and assist the functioning capacities of which they are expression and realization. The skills are acquired by an individual with education, systematic effort and exercise within the formal education, but they are also acquired in non-formal education through experiential learning and involvement with events and situations (Schneider & Byrne, 1995; Romanczyk, et al., 2005).

Self-awareness refers to the capacity to recognize and understand emotions and to have a sense of how one's actions, moods and the emotions of others take effect. It involves keeping track of emotions and noticing different emotional reactions, as well as being able to identify the emotions correctly. Self-awareness also includes recognizing that how we feel and what we do are related, and having awareness of one's own personal strengths and limitations. Self-awareness is associated with being open to different experiences and new ideas and learning from social interactions. Self-awareness is a key component for managing stress, avoiding burnout, and thriving in the classroom. It is the ability to recognize emotions and thoughts, how they influence behaviour, and making accurate assessments of our strengths and limitations.

Theoretically, behaviourists believe that high efficiency can be achieved in an environment through an appropriate leaning of the required behavioural patterns that

should be reinforced adequately. From a different perspective, the humanist while seeing the human person as a proactive agent moving towards self-actualization opined that adequate Social Studies teachers Proficiency is attainable when significant order in the environment provide unconditional positive regard to the learning process. The conceptualization of the framework of this study is based on the behaviourist theory propounded by Ivan Pavlov (1927). The behavioural theory stipulates that behaviour is learned as a result of exposure to stimulus and the individual's reaction to the situation would lead to a response in order words leaning takes place when Students are motivated to learn.

The behaviourist theory emphasizes the importance of observing and modeling the behaviours, attitudes and emotional reactions of others. Learning would be exceedingly laborious, not to mention hazardous, if people had relied solely on the effect of their own action to inform them what to do. The theory explains human behaviour in terms of continuous reciprocal interaction between cognitive, behavioural and environmental influences. significant to the promotion of Students' learning outcome in School subjects including Social Studies. Therefore, the spot light is no the need to create learning environment if there would be improved academic performance among Secondary School Students. Social Studies teacher, as an implementation agent, is expected to play his/her role in the achievement of the policy objectives. According to the policy document, the major pursuit of government towards the classroom teacher in Nigerian Schools includes to: produce highly motivated, conscientious and efficient classroom teachers for all levels of our education system; encourage further spirit of enquiry and creativity in teachers; help teachers fit into the social life of the community and society at large and to enhance their commitment to national objectives; provide (competent) teachers with intellectual and professional background adequate for their assignment and to make them adaptable to any changing situation not only in the life of their country, but also in the whole world; and enhance teachers' commitment to the teaching profession.

This component of EI refers to interacting well with other people. It involves applying an understanding of the emotions of ourselves and others to communicate and interact with others on a day-to-day basis and this requires the help of social skills. Different social skills include – active listening, verbal communication skills, non-verbal communication skills, leadership, and developing rapport. Teaching social and emotional skills in the classroom can help Students grow into empathetic, kind and

selfless adults. Meanwhile, empathy is key to an equitable world, social and emotional skills aren't limited to relationships with others. In fact, they're deeply rooted in our relationships with ourselves. The goals and objectives of education provide grounds for effective management of materials and human beings. In the management of materials, emphasis is laid of School facilities. These facilities range from residential, administrative and academic facilities.

Cooper (2016) in his research, show that individuals with higher Self-awareness are likely to be more successful in life, work and are more likely to build stronger interpersonal relationships than those with low Self-awareness. Individuals who have high Self-awareness will control their emotions better, excel in jobs and can also unlock the potential of those around. In every human relationship such as workplace, communication is something that must go on. It has been observed that good interpersonal communication will substantially contributes to effective organizational performance.

Interpersonal communication among staffs may fail to serve its purpose when too many symbolic gestures are used, lack of language and listening skills. Scholars collectively have identified with and used interpersonal communication to describe their workplace performance. Good interpersonal communication should be encouraged at work as this is a means organizations mission and vision statement can be expressed. Kasinath (2019) studied interactive effect of Social Skills, Self-awareness, mental health, and social-economic status on adjustment with the objective to find out the difference among Students who were well adapted to School environment differ in their Self-awareness by taking a sample of 200 Students (102 boys and 98 girls) and found that students having better social and emotional students attain good academic scores.

The absence of social skills and self-awareness in Social Studies teachers may affect student's social adjustments in school, this is evidenced through the result released from their internal and external examinations among public secondary schools in Nigeria. Most students in Nigerian secondary schools are at great risk of poor adjustment to school and this is attributed to so many reasons, some of the reasons according to Okoro (2020), includes poor teaching approaches and methodology, teachers unpreparedness and lack of knowledge of the topic, wrong instructional materials, lack of emotional control transfer of negative emotions and anger, lack of motivational and evaluation skills, poor classroom management, lack of regular in-

service training programme, and poor teachers supervision. The study investigated social skills, self -awareness of Social Studies teachers and social adjustment of upper basic Social Studies students in Delta State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. determine the relationship between social skills of Social Studies teachers social adjustment of students in upper basic schools; and
- ii. examine the relationship between self -awareness of Social Studies teachers and social adjustment of students in upper basic schools.

Hypotheses

The following hypothesis were formulated to guide the study.

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between social skills of Social Studies teachers and social adjustment of upper basic Social Studies students in Delta State.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between self –awareness of Social Studies teachers and social adjustment of upper basic Social Studies students in Delta State.

Methods

This study adopted correlational research design. This type of study is used to establish the relationship between two or more variables. Usually, such studies indicate the direction and magnitude of the relationship between the variables. Nworgu (2016) opined that all predictive studies are correlation studies. The design will enable the researcher to collect original data from the respondents directly and describe the present condition as they exist in their natural setting. The population of the study consists of 385 upper basic school social studies teachers of Delta State and the data generated indicated that there are 435 Secondary Schools in Delta State with 6,696 population of Students for the year 2023.

Table 1: Shows how the Population of the study was generated

S/N	Senatorial Districts	Population of Social Studies Teachers	Population of Students
1	North	152	3496
2	South	116	1616
3	Central	117	1611
Total		385	6696

The techniques adapted for sampling of sample in the study were the stratified random sampling techniques which involve the use of tailoring procedure for the study. The

instrument for data collection were questionnaire and Social Studies students examination score and grade for basic eight, 2022/2023 academic session. A standardized questionnaire developed by Studsrod and Bru (2009) was adapted for the study designed to be administered to Social Studies Teachers and Students respectively. The instrument contains 40 items. 30 items measured self-awareness and 10 items measured social Skills of Social Studies teachers, why Social Studies Student examination score and grade was and to measure of student in upper basic schools. The instruments for data collection were face and content validated by experts in guidance and counseling, and measurement and evaluation. The instruments were showed to experts for scrutiny in order to ascertain the clarity, relevance, and adequacy. The study employed correlation coefficient of determination, regression analysis and F-test were Used to test the stated hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between social skills of Social Studies teachers and social adjustment of students in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Table 2: Linear Regression Analysis of Social Skills and Social adjustment of Student in upper basic Schools in Delta State

Model summary

R	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
.380	0.145	0.141	4.31477

Anova

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	749.089	1	749.089	40.236	0.000
Resident	4430.911	238	18.617		
Total	515.000	239			

Coefficients

	Unstandard Coefficient		Standard Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	
(Constant)	33.266	2.339		14.220	0.000
Social Skills	0.451	0.071	0.380	6.343	0.000

Table 2 indicates a linear regression output of a relationship between social skills and social adjustment of students in upper basic schools in Delta State. The computed F-value of 40.236 and a p-value of 0.000. Testing the hypothesis at an alpha level of 0.05, the p-value of 0.000 was less than the alpha level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implied that there was significant relationship between Social Skills and Social adjustment of Students in upper basic Schools in Delta State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between self-awareness of Social Studies teachers and social adjustment of student in upper basic schools.

Table 3: Linear Regression Analysis of Self-awareness and Social adjustment of Student in upper basic Schools in Delta State

Model Summary

R	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
0.053	0.003	0.001	4.65880

Anova

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	14.339	1	14.339	0.661	0.417
Resident	5165.661	238	21.704		
Total	5180.000	239			

Coefficients

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	
(Constant)	47.295	0.918		51.545	0.000
Social Skills	0.494	0.608	0.053	0.813	0.417

Table 3 shows a linear regression output of a relationship between self-awareness of Social Studies teachers and social adjustment of students in upper basic schools. The computed F- value of 0.661 and a p-value of 0.417. Testing the hypothesis at an alpha level of 0.05, the p-value of 0.417 was greater than the alpha level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implied that there was no significant relationship

between self-awareness and social adjustment of students in upper basic Schools. Hence, self-awareness of Social Studies teachers was not significant at an alpha level of 0.05.

Discussions

The findings indicated that there was significant relationship between social skills, and social adjustment of students in upper basic schools in Delta State. This showed that social skills are related to the ability for an individual to manage or control his emotions in a healthy and productive manner. This finding supports the study of Mahesh (2015) who investigated 240 students on social skills and social adjustment of students in upper basic schools and found that social skills had significant influence on social adjustment of students in upper basic schools.

The findings indicated that there was significant relationship between self-awareness and social adjustment of students in upper basic schools in Delta State. The result of the finding is also in consonance with Adeyemo (2010) who studied the relationship between self-awareness and social adjustment of students in upper basic schools on a sample of 200 students. The result showed that the strength of self-awareness significantly impacted on the social adjustment of students in upper basic schools in Delta State

Conclusion

Arising from the findings of this study, it was concluded that employing the services of emotional intelligent teachers and as well as teachers who are well adapted to the working conditions as contained in the teaching profession will greatly enhance students' social adjustment when employed to teach Social Studies. Furthermore, it was discovered that self-awareness level of Social Studies teachers contributes a lot to the students' level of assimilation of contents taught in Social Studies.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the study recommended that teachers of Social Studies and counselors should try to inculcate high social skills into their students to facilitate their quick smooth adjustment to School. Social Studies teacher should be passionate about the teaching job. Teachers should handle their students as their own children. Social Studies Teachers should be encouraged to adopt positive and high social skills through interaction with their students.

References

- Anakwe, A. (2012). Factorial validity of a school adjustment school for adolescents in Metanustate. *The Educational psychologist*, 6 (1) 30-88.
- Atubi, F. O. (2024). Analysis of cognitive achievement of Social Studies student: perspectives of gender and school location. *Journal of African Social Studies* 5(1)31-44.
- Cooper, C (2016). Pre-adolescent friendship and peer rejection as predictors of adult adjustment. *Child Development* 69, 140-153.
- Kasinath, C. (2019). Assessing transitions to middle and high School. *Journal of Adolescent Research; 19* (1), 3-30.
- Goleman (2019). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioural change. *Psychological Review*, 2, 191-215.
- Okoro, P. (2020). Research recommendations. *Advance in Child Development*, 30, 275-310.
- Schneider, B., & Romanczyk, W. G. (2005) School effects on psychological outcomes during adolescence. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 94 (2) 795-808.
- Wahlster, Kully-Martenset. al. (2012). Peer group pressure as a department of adolescent social adjustment in Nigeria schools. Department of Educational Foundations. Faculty of Education University of Lagos.